

EDUCATIONAL QUALITY MANAGEMENT: A PRACTICAL APPROACH

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Annotation: The article concentrates on fundamentality of educational content, comprehensive approach to management, interdisciplinary integration, proportionality of goals and results, satisfaction of certain needs, independent work of learners, and creative activity of participants of the educational process. There are various point of views on how to describe the relationships between others. A primary emphasis in the article lies on management of educational quality.

Key words: quality management, competitiveness, Total Quality Control, Organization for Standardization, monitoring.

One of the crucial factors for the country to develop successfully is high-quality education. In turn, a quality educational environment is required to train professional specialists. One of the urgent issues of today is the training of quality specialists.

The quality of education is not only the compliance of students' knowledge with the state standards, but also the successful operation of the educational institution, as well as the activity of each pedagogue and leader in ensuring the quality of educational services.

The quality of education in a modern educational institution is defined as the ratio of goals and results expressed in a set of descriptions that reflect the level of quantitative and qualitative results, the level of organization and implementation of the educational process, the conditions under which it takes place.

Management of educational quality (educational quality management) is part of the general structure of educational management. In this case, the management of the quality of education does not deny the linear structure of management, in which the leader's sole leadership is of decisive importance and has shown its effectiveness in practice. In its place, the introduction of quality management significantly increases the efficiency of general management - regulates relations between the head of the educational institution, employees and representatives of interested public organizations. The sequence of tasks, the tasks themselves, the ways of execution, the detailed order of individual methods and actions, as a basis for ensuring the quality of education, guarantee the effective implementation of the management decisions.

Therefore, the management of the quality of education complements the existing theory and practice of management activities in the educational system with important elements, that is, it is implemented as a component of the integrated system of educational management. The logic of the development of the system of ensuring the quality of education, based on a systematic and objective assessment of the activity of the educational institution with the involvement of an external audit of the quality of education, dictates the development and implementation of the system of management of the quality of education in educational institutions.

In addition, the existence of the educational quality management system in educational institutions creates the opportunity to replace the external control measures of the quality and results of the educational process in the future with the use of internal control and self-assessment results, and the openness of these processes to public control increases the level of confidence in the educational institution.

The period of rapid development of the theory of quality management coincided with the end of the 40s and 50s of the last century. During this period, A. Feigenbaum (Armand V. Feigenbaum) introduced the concept of Total Quality Control (TQC for short), consisting of the stages of quality development, quality support and quality improvement. To date, there are several main "schools" of TQC (Japan, America, Europe). Therefore, there is no consensus among experts on the number of principles that underlie TQC. In many countries of the world, quality improvement has become a national idea as a result of the efforts of the government, firms and companies' management aimed at ensuring the high quality of products, services, work and processes. As a result of the integration of different approaches, the concept of Total Quality Management (TQM) was formed. The basis of modern TQM is the development of a long-term strategy in the field of quality for the benefit of the organization, its employees, consumers and society, and the participation of all employees in its implementation. Permanent and regular personal participation of the management of the educational institution in quality management is a guarantee of success in the quality assurance work of the educational institution. To implement total quality management, the followings should be taken into consideration:

Introduction of quality management, adoption of a strategic decision on the development of the purpose, general ideology, development principles of the educational institution in competitive conditions;

Include quality assurance in the organization's goals, to support it both morally and materially;

Appoint a representative responsible for quality from the top management of the organization;

Training of employees (including senior managers) in the areas of statistical process management and quality management;

Organizing feedback with employees (taking into account the opinions and demands of internal consumers);

The concept of TQM reflects all the positive aspects characteristic of previous concepts of quality management. It forms the basis of many modern management systems in the field of production and service. The importance of standards is that they introduce a systematic approach to enterprise management, focusing management's attention on consumers and taking into account the interests of all interested parties. The 9000 digital standards of the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) introduced a single, globally recognized approach to the design and implementation of quality systems. The experience of implementing the educational quality management system in developed countries makes it possible to distinguish the following main stages of quality management:

Designing the education quality management system of the educational institution and planning the management of the quality of education is forming the normative, organizational, methodological and instrumental bases of activities to achieve the required quality.

Quality management of education is formation of quality reflecting the sequence of regular activities on studying the needs of customers of educational services, development and implementation of basic and additional education programs, education with resources provisioning processes.

Process monitoring and making changes (Control and Action) - the process of comparing and evaluating the achieved level of quality with the set level, making feedback to all interested parties, making changes to the management system and activities.

Thus, educational quality management is a continuous and closed process consisting of interconnected and interacting elements.

The goal of creating an educational quality management system in an educational institution is to provide the necessary conditions for providing quality educational services that meet the needs of consumers.

In addition, the educational quality management systems in a modern educational institution is necessary and below its advantages are listed:

Increase the effectiveness of educational processes in meeting the requirements of state educational standards;

Development of a creative and working environment in the institution, increasing the professional activity of employees;

Improving the management system in the educational institution;

Optimization of financial, material and personnel support of the educational process;

Increase the competitiveness of the educational institution;

Creation of modern security conditions for educational activities;

The tasks of the education quality management system in an educational institution are as follows:

Determining the main criteria indicators of the quality of education in an educational institution;

Preparation of analytical reports and lectures on the quality of education in the educational institution;

Encourage innovative processes in the educational institution to ensure and continuously improve the quality of education;

Determining the directions of development of the educational institution, improving the qualifications of pedagogical staff.

Based on the above, we can conclude that quality management of education in an educational institution is planning, i.e. setting educational goals and ways to achieve them; organizing the educational process and arousing the interest of its participants in quality work; system for identifying deviations from goals and monitoring changes in development (monitoring); results management and analysis processes. Moreover, educational quality management means the implementation of all management functions to achieve the specified indicators, to achieve a guaranteed result in both the narrow and broad sense.

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